

The Effect of Transparency, Accountability, Supervision, and Community Participation on Budget Management

Desi Kirana Putri¹

¹⁾ University of Jember, Kalimantan Street No. 37, East Krajan, Sumbersari, Sumbersari District, Jember, East Java, Indonesia

Email: kirana.desinana@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

Public sector accounting is accounting used by a public institution or an organization to account for what has been done to the public. One part of the public sector is the Regional Planning and Development Agency (BAPPEDA). Bappededa in carrying out good budget management must apply the principles of transparency, accountability, supervision and community participation. This study aims to determine the effect of transparency, accountability, supervision and community participation on the management of the budget for assistance to the poor. The population in this study were all employees of Bappededa Situbondo Regency. The sampling technique used was *purposive sampling* with primary data collection by distributing questionnaires according to the criteria of the research sample. The total research sample according to the researcher's criteria is 40 respondents. The data analysis method used is quantitative research with descriptive statistical testing, data instrument testing, classical assumption testing and hypothesis testing. The results of this study indicate that there is a insignificant effect of the variables of transparency, accountability and public participation on the management of the budget for assistance to the poor, while for the supervision variable there is a significant influence on the management of the budget for assistance to the poor.

1. INTRODUCTION

Public sector accounting is accounting used by a public institution or an organization to account for what has been done to the public and has a goal that does not prioritize profit and is one of the scientific disciplines (Satriawan and Pertiwi 2015). Public institutions or organizations are required by the community to manage budgets in an accountable, transparent, and responsible manner (Roziq, Sofianti, et al. 2019). In this case, a very critical community request can result in the local government having to provide excellent service and show good performance to the community, as one of the public sector organizations (Purniawan, Mas'ud, and

Wulandari 2019). So the government is required to work in accordance with the wishes and interests of the community (Arifani, Salle, and Rante 2018).

One part of the public sector, namely the Regional Development Planning Agency (BAPPEDA) is a technical institution which is in charge of the research and development planning process of a region or village as well as providing assistance to the poor or underprivileged (Kustono, Mas'ud, and Magvira 2019). It can be seen that the public sector which is part of the Regional Government Work Unit has always been in the spotlight by the public (Sulistiyono, al Ardi, and Roziq 2020). Because there have been many cases such as leakage of funds, inefficiency,

waste of costs and always experiencing very significant losses (Kustono and Nanggala 2020). To minimize this occurrence, part of the public sector also gets demands to improve services, so it is necessary to apply the concept of value for money in carrying out an activity that has been determined (Kustono 2020).

Based on this background, researchers are interested in conducting research with the aim of knowing the Effect of Transparency, Accountability, Supervision and Community Participation on Budget Management at the Regional Development Planning Agency of Situbondo Regency (Kusuma, Putra, and Sudarno 2021). The results of this study are expected to add insight and knowledge, especially regarding budget management in a government agency.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES

Theoretical Foundation

Good Corporate Governance (GCG)

According to the Decree of the Minister of State-Owned Enterprises No.117/2002, corporate governance is a structure and process used by *BUMN* organizations to improve business success and organizational accountability (Miqdad and Rizky Izzalqurny 2019). So that it can realize shareholder value in the long term (Prasetyo et al. 2020). And by looking at stakeholder interests in accordance with laws and regulations and ethical values (Luthfiyatul Farida, Roziq, and Maria Wardayati 2019).

Stewardship Theory

Stewardship theory suggests that the situation of management is not motivated by individual goals but is more focused on the main goal, namely the interests of the organization (Donaldson and Davis 1991). According to (Jefri 2018), stewardship theory sees management as the backbone of the company's success, management's success in achieving company goals can improve the welfare of shareholders and managers of the organization (Afifi, Kustono, and Nuha 2022).

Supervision

Supervision is something to observe events and compare them with what should have happened (Sudewi et al. 2017). Supervision is a process for making decisions and determining performance measures (Santosa Putra et al.

2020). So that it can support the achievement of results as expected and set (Arifani et al. 2018).

Society Participation

Community participation is the role played by the community and the empowerment given to the community in the process of budgeting and implementing the program (Putra and Rasmini 2019). Community participation is community members who are involved in a program carried out by the government (Prasetyo 2019).

Budget Management

Management is a series of businesses or work carried out by an organization that has the principle of achieving the planned goals that are based on planning, organizing, movement and supervision (Sudewi et al. 2017). Management is a series of businesses that have the aim of utilizing and exploring all potentials efficiently and effectively to achieve the goals that have been set (Maulamin, Cholik, and Alawiah 2018).

Hypothesis Development

The effect of transparency on budget management

Transparency is one of the factors for good budget management for a government agency, if the government agency has a higher level of transparency, the budget management will tend to be better or more effective (Roziq and Sukarno 2021). This is in accordance with the theory of stewardship which explains that an organization is not motivated by individual goals but rather by organizational goals (Hidayatullah, Budi Sulistiyo, and Hisamuddin Jurusan Akuntansi 2019).

In achieving these organizational goals, it is necessary to apply the transparency principle from Bappeda Situbondo which is given to stakeholders, so that stewards will be motivated to achieve good performance (Nuha, Miqdad, and Sulistiyo 2021). This will have an impact on the satisfaction obtained by stakeholders regarding the needs being met (Putri, Miqdad, and Sulistiyo 2020a). Research results from (Putra and Rasmini 2019) state that transparency significantly affects budget management. This is also similar to the results of research conducted by (Satriawan and Pertiwi 2015) which states that transparency is very influential on budget management with the concept of value for money. From the results of

these studies, the following hypotheses can be proposed:

H1: Transparency has a positive effect on budget management

Effect of accountability on budget management

The principle of accountability when linked to stewardship theory is appropriate, it can be seen that accountability is a form of accountability from Bappeda Situbondo regarding budget management activities to stakeholders (Maulidah and Winarno 2022). If the implementation of the accountability principle is done well, the stewards can be motivated to achieve good organizational performance (List, Arif, and Santosa Putra 2022). This will have an impact on stakeholder satisfaction by meeting their needs (Irmadariyani et al. 2019). The results of research from (Sains 2018) state that accountability affects budget management significantly. This research is also supported by (Satriawan and Pertiwi 2015) which states that accountability has an influence on budget management with the concept of value for money.

H2: Accountability has a positive effect on budget management

Effect of supervision on budget management

Supervision if it is associated with stewardship theory is appropriate, it can be seen from if the supervision carried out by stakeholders to a government agency (Kurrohman 2020). The steward will be motivated to achieve good performance in order to achieve goals in the organization (As sajad, Puspita, and Sudarno 2021). This will also have an impact on the satisfaction that will be received by stakeholders regarding the fulfillment of the expected needs (Adita, Irmadariyani, and Shulthoni 2021). The results of research by (Sudewi et al. 2017) state that supervision in each public sector has an effect on budget management with the concept of value for money. The higher the supervision, the higher the budget management (Purnamawati et al. 2019). From the results of the research above, the following hypotheses can be proposed:

H3: Supervision has a positive effect on budget management

The influence of community participation on budget management

Community participation if it is associated with stewardship theory is appropriate (Kusuma and Shulthoni 2021). It can be seen from if stakeholders participate well in the programs carried out by Bappeda Situbondo, the stewards will have high motivation in good budget management (Roos Ana, Budi Sulistiyo, and Prasetyo 2021). This will have an impact on the achievement of Bappeda's goals, vision and mission and the satisfaction obtained by stakeholders (Ely, Effendi, and Mas'ud 2019). The results of the research from (Putra and Rasmini 2019) stated that community participation had a positive effect on the effectiveness of fund management. This research is also supported by (Masruhin and Kaukab 2019), community participation has a positive effect on fund management.

H4: Community participation has a positive effect on budget management

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This research was conducted using a quantitative approach. The population used in this study were all employees of the Regional Development Planning Agency of Situbondo Regency (Putri, Miqdad, and Sulistiyo 2020b). The criteria for this research sample are purposive sampling of permanent employees of the Regional Development Planning Agency of Situbondo Regency (Agus Winarno et al. 2021). The respondents used in this study are permanent employees of the Regional Development Planning Agency of Situbondo Regency (Roziq, Marizca, and Kustono 2021). This study uses a data source, namely primary data which is a source of research data obtained directly from the original source (Roziq, Abshor, et al. 2019). The data analysis method used in this research is using empirical studies, using several tests, namely descriptive statistical tests, validity and reliability tests, normality tests, multicollinearity tests, heteroscedasticity tests, multiple linear regression analysis, model tests and T-tests.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The object of this research is the Regional Development Planning Agency of Situbondo Regency. The data in this study were collected by sending a questionnaire in the form of a google form to respondents to fill out.

a. Descriptive Statistical Analysis

No.	N	Min	Max	Median	Mean	Std. Deviation
Transparansi	40	14	25	19,5	20,38	2,667
Akuntabilitas	40	17	35	26	27,68	4,153
Pengawasan	40	11	25	20,5	19,60	2,916
Partisipasi masyarakat	40	12	19	15	15,43	1,907
Pengelolaan Anggaran	40	12	20	17	17,15	2,190

Sumber: Hasil olah data SPSS 23.0

Figure 1. Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistical analysis is used to determine the amount of data, range, mean value, minimum and maximum value, variance, standard deviation in a study. The variables in this study include: transparency, accountability, supervision, community participation and budget management (Suyitno, Miqdad, and Sayekti 2020).

b. Classical Assumption Test/Normality Test

One sample kolmogorov-smirnov test	N	Sig	Keterangan
Transparansi	40	.200	Data berdistribusi normal
Akuntabilitas	40	.200	Data berdistribusi normal
Pengawasan	40	.200	Data berdistribusi normal
Partisipasi Masyarakat	40	.200	Data berdistribusi normal

Sumber: Data primer hasil olah data SPSS 23.0, 2021

Figure 2. Normality Test

The test results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov significance value of 0.200 are great than the alpha of 0.05, which means that the residual data used in this study is normally distributed so that the regression model is feasible to use in this study.

Variabel independen	Tolerance	VIF	Keterangan
Transparansi	.340	2,939	Tidak terjadi multikolinearitas
Akuntabilitas	.344	2,909	Tidak terjadi multikolinearitas
Pengawasan	.303	3,296	Tidak terjadi multikolinearitas
Partisipasi	.508	1,969	Tidak terjadi

Figure 3. Multicollinearity Test

The tolerance value for all independent variables in this study has a value greater than 0.1 and the VIF (variance inflation factor) value for all independent variables is less than 10, so it can be concluded that the regression model in this study does not show symptoms of multicollinearity between independent variables been tested.

Variabel dependen	Variabel independen	Sig.	Keterangan
Pengelolaan Anggaran	Transparansi	.844	Bebas heteroskedastisitas
	Akuntabilitas	.971	Bebas heteroskedastisitas
	Pengawasan	.950	Bebas heteroskedastisitas
	Partisipasi Masyarakat	.633	Bebas heteroskedastisitas

Sumber: Data primer hasil olah data SPSS 23.0, 2021

Figure 4. Heterocedasticity Test

All independent variables have a significance value of more than 0.05, so from these results it can be concluded that the regression model in this study is free or does not occur heteroscedasticity symptoms.

c. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Model	Undstandar dized		Sandardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
1 (constant)	2,533	2,050	Beta	1,236	,225
Transparansi	-,095	,167	-,096	-,566	,575
Akuntabilitas	,163	,107	,259	1,529	,135
Pengawasan	,659	,162	,733	4,069	,000
Partisipasi Masyarakat	-,075	,120	-,087	-,625	,536

a. Dependen variabel : Pengelolaan anggaran

Figure 5. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

The regression constant is 2.533 which means that the independent variables are considered constant, so budget management (Y) is 2.533.

d. Hypothesis testing

Model	R Square
1	.655

Sumber: Data primer hasil olah data SPSS 23.0, 2021

Figure 6. Determinant Coefficient Analysis

The value of R square is 0.655. This means that the dependent variable, namely budget management, can be explained by four independent variables, namely transparency, accountability, supervision and community participation with a percentage of 65.5%, while the rest (100%-65.5%) of 34.5% can be explained by other variables outside the research model.

e. Model Test

Model	Sig.
1	.000

Sumber: Data primer hasil olah data SPSS 23.0, 2021

Figure 7. Model Test

The significance value is less than 0.05, so it can be concluded that the independent variables, namely transparency,

accountability, supervision and community participation simultaneously or simultaneously affect budget management.

f. T test

Variabel	t	Sig.
Transparansi	-.566	.575
Akuntabilitas	1.529	.135
Pengawasan	4.069	.000
Partisipasi Masyarakat	-.625	.536

Sumber: Data primer hasil olah data SPSS 23.0, 2021

Figure 8. T test

The results of the partial t-test, show that transparency, accountability and public participation have no effect on budget management, but supervision has a positive and significant effect on budget management.

The Effect of Transparency on Budget Management

The results of hypothesis testing indicate that transparency has no effect on budget management in Bappeda Situbondo. This can be seen from the results of $t\text{-count} < t\text{-table}$, namely $-0.566 < 2.0243$ and a significance of 0.575. In addition, the results of the analysis are also supported by the unstandardized coefficients B value of -0.095, which means that transparency affects the management of the disbursed budget of -0.095. The value of -0.095 is negative, meaning that the lower the transparency, the lower the budget management.

Based on this research, transparency has no effect on budget management. Based on the results of the questionnaire, it shows that Bappeda Situbondo in realizing relevant, reliable, and accurate budget management practices is still not transparent, it can be seen from the statement of the questionnaire that the annual budget accountability report is always given on time to the public, the majority of respondents answered neutrally. The results of this study are supported by research conducted by (Laoli 2019) and (Sukmawati and Nurfitriani 2019) which states that partially transparency has no significant effect on budget management.

Effect of Accountability on Budget Management

Based on the results of the tests that have been carried out, it shows that accountability has no effect on budget management, this shows that accountability does not guarantee that budget management is getting better, this can also be seen from the results of the questionnaire on the

statement items in evaluating the budget, only comparing targets with actual low scores with neutral respondents' answers compared to other indicators because accountability regarding the interests of the community and groups in obtaining the budget has not become the main interest. The results of this study are supported by research conducted by (Arifani et al. 2018) and (Sinaga 2017).

Effect of Supervision on Budget Management

In this study, supervision affects budget management, this is in accordance with the third hypothesis that supervision has a positive effect on budget management. Based on the results of the questionnaire, there are statements with the majority of respondents' answers agreeing, namely the statement that budget supervision in Bappeda Situbondo is carried out by the Regional Inspectorate on a regular basis, its shows that supervision at Bappeda Situbondo has been carried out well. The results of this study are supported by research conducted by (Sudewi et al. 2017) and (Satriawan and Pertiwi 2015) which state that partially, supervision has a positive and significant effect on budget management.

The Effect of Community Participation on Budget Management

In this study, community participation does not significantly affect budget management, this is not in accordance with the fourth hypothesis that public participation has a positive effect on budget management. Based on the results of the questionnaire on the statement item, namely that the recipient community was directly involved in making decisions on the preparation of Bappeda Situbondo programs, the majority of respondents answered numbers two and three or disagreed and were neutral. This shows that the community does not participate in the program that has been provided by the Bappeda Situbondo. Community participation during planning activities is still relatively low and this is influenced by several factors, namely, the willingness of community representatives, socialization and relations with government officials. The results of this study are supported by research by (Nurkhasanah 2019) which states that partially public participation does not affect budget management in an accountability manner.

5. CONCLUSION, IMPLICATION, SUGGESTION, AND LIMITATIONS

CONCLUSION

Transparency does not have a significant effect on budget management in Bappeda Situbondo, although it has no effect, the principle of transparency must be applied in budget management to provide clear information regarding the objectives, targets, results and benefits of the budget. Accountability does not have a significant effect on budget management in Bappeda Situbondo, although it has no effect, the principle of accountability must be applied in budget management to realize Good Corporate Governance.

Supervision has a positive and significant influence on budget management in Bappeda Situbondo. This shows the supervision of a system that is very important to oversee the activities carried out in a government agency by comparing the implementation that has been carried out with the planned. Community participation does not have a significant influence on budget management in Bappeda Situbondo. This can be caused by several factors, namely the lack of public will and socialization.

SUGGESTIONS

Future researchers are expected to be able to collect data with various data collection methods, not only using questionnaires. For further researchers, it is hoped that they can add research samples not only at the Regional Development Planning Agency of Situbondo Regency, but also to be able to conduct research in other districts that get the best achievements. For further researchers, it is expected to add independent variables other than those contained in the study such as organizational culture, leadership style and so on.

LIMITATIONS

The data collection technique used was only distributing questionnaires through google form so that it could lead to a lack of good enough communication between researchers and respondents. This is because the research was conducted during a pandemic. This research was only conducted at the Regional Development Planning Agency of Situbondo Regency. The variables used in this study are limited, consisting of transparency, accountability, supervision and community participation.

REFERENCES

- Adita, Shofiahtu, Ririn Irmadariyani, and Moch Shulthoni. 2021. "Pengaruh Pengungkapan Shari'ah Corporate Social Responsibility Terhadap Kinerja Keuangan." *Jurnal Akuntansi Universitas Jember* 19(1).
- Afifi, Muhammad Ghazi Falih, Alwan Sri Kustono, and Gardina Aulin Nuha. 2022. "Pengaruh Penerapan Laporan Arus Kas Operasi, Economic Value Added, Dan Laba Kotor Terhadap Volume Perdagangan Saham Pada Perusahaan Properti Dan Real Estate Di Bursa Efek Indonesia." *Juremi: Jurnal Riset Ekonimi* 1(4).
- Arifani, Cindy, Agustinus Salle, and Andika Rante. 2018. "PENGARUH AKUNTABILITAS, TRANSPARANSI DA PENGAWASAN TERHADAP KINERJA ANGGARAN BERBASIS VALUE FOR MONEY." *Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Daerah* 13(1):68–82.
- As sajad, Mudrika Berliana, Dewi Ayu Puspita, and Sudarno. 2021. "Pengaruh Corporate Social Responsibility Sebagai Deductible Expense Terhadap Agresivitas Pajak Pada Perusahaan Pertambangan." *Jurnal Akuntansi Universitas Jember* 19(2).
- Donaldson, Lex, and James H. Davis. 1991. "Stewardship Theory or Agency Theory: CEO Governance and Shareholder Returns." *Australian Journal of Management* 16(1):49–64.
- Ely, Mira, Rochman Effendi, and Imam Mas'ud. 2019. "Penerapan Metode Time Driven Activity Based Costing (TDABC) Dalam Perhitungan Kos Service Pada Bengkel HBBA." *Jurnal Akuntansi Universitas Jember* 17(2).
- Hidayatullah, Arif, Agung Budi Sulistiyo, and Nur Hisamuddin Jurusan Akuntansi. 2019. "Analisis Rekonstruksi Penyusunan Laporan Keuangan Masjid (Studi Kasus Pada Masjid Agung Baiturrahman Banyuwangi)Mosque)." *E-Journal Ekonomi Bisnis Dan Akuntansi* VI(1):69–75.

- Irmadariyani, Ririn, Isti Fadah, Diana K. Sulianti Tobing, and Siti Maria Wardayati. 2019. "Empirical Investigation Of The Role Of Sharia's Corporate Social Responsibility On The Relationship Between Firm Size And Profitability." *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC & TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH* 8:7.
- Jefri, Riny. 2018. "Teori Stewardship Dan Good Governance." *Economics Bosowa* 4(3):14–28.
- Kurrohman, Taufik. 2020. "Akad Pembiayaan Syariah Yang Sesuai Dengan Maqasid Syariah Dalam Perbankan Syariah." *Jurnal Surya Kencana Satu* 11(1):115–28.
- Kustono, Alwan Sri. 2020. "Motive behind Earnings Management Practices: Case in Public Property and Real Estate Companies in Indonesia." *AKRUAL: Jurnal Akuntansi* 12(1):49. doi: 10.26740/jaj.v12n1.p49-64.
- Kustono, Alwan Sri, Imam Mas'ud, and Dwima Nadya Magvira. 2019. "Target Costing to Manage Production Cost in Cassava Fermented SMEs Case in 'Kembang Madu' Tapay Industry-Indonesia." in *Proceeding of The 3rd International Conference on Accounting, Business & Economics*.
- Kustono, Alwan Sri, and Ardhya Yudhistira Adi Nanggala. 2020. "Activity Based Costing Dengan Kendali Waktu Untuk Menghitung Cost Layanan Pada Bengkel Otomotif 'DA' Di Jember." *EL MUHASABA* 11(1).
- Kusuma, Ahmad Ahsin, and Moch. Shulthoni. 2021. "Analysis of Information Technology Development in Management Accounting." *The International Journal of Business & Management* 9(6). doi: 10.24940/theijbm/2021/v9/i6/bm2106-009.
- Kusuma, Andre, Hendrawan Santosa Putra, and Sudarno. 2021. "Rekam Jejak Dan Potensi Penelitian Di Badan Usaha Milik Desa: Studi Bibliometrik Publikasi Tahun 2015-2020." *Jurnal Akuntansi Universitas Jember* 19(2).
- Laoli, Victorinus. 2019. "Pengaruh Akuntabilitas Dan Transparansi Terhadap Kinerja Anggaran Berkonsep Value of Money Pada Pemerintah Kabupaten Nias." *Owner: Riset Dan Jurnal Akuntansi* 3(1):91–102.
- List, Author, Alfi Arif, and Hendrawan Santosa Putra. 2022. "Analysis of PSAK 71 Implementation on Allowance for Impairment of Financial Assets." *VALUE: Journal of Business Studies* 1(1).
- Luthfiyatul Farida, Ajeng, Ahmad Roziq, and Siti Maria Wardayati. 2019. "Determinant Variables Of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM), Audit Opinions And Company Value On Insurance Emitents Listed In Indonesia Stock Exchange." *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC & TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH* 8:7.
- Masruhin, Anam, and M. Elfan Kaukab. 2019. "Pengaruh Kompetensi Aparatur, Komitmen Organisasi, Partisipasi Masyarakat, Dan Kejelasan Sasaran Anggaran Terhadap Pengelolaan Dana Desa (Studi Empiris Pada Perangkat Desa Di Kecamatan Mojotengah Kabupaten Wonosobo)." *Journal of Economic, Business and Engineering (JEBE)* 1(1):118–30.
- Maulamin, Taufan, Agus Cholik, and Eneng Tuti Alawiah. 2018. "Pengaruh Prinsip-Prinsip Good Corporate Governance Terhadap Pengelolaan Anggaran Pada Instansi Pemerintah (Studi Pada Dinas Pengelolaan Keuangan, Pendapatan Dan Aset Kabupaten Pandeglang Provinsi Banten)." *Transparansi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Administrasi* 1(2):259–82.
- Maulidah, Ilmia, and Wahyu Agus Winarno. 2022. "Kajian Literatur Dan Sintesis Environmental Management Accounting (EMA): Sebuah Studi Reviu Sistematis." *Akuntansi Dan Teknologi Informasi* 15(1):34–61. doi: 10.24123/jati.v15i1.4845.
- Miqdad, Muhammad, and Tomy Rizky Izzalqurny. 2019. "Urgensi Implementasi Laporan Berkelanjutan (Sustainability Reports) Di Perguruan Tinggi." *Jurnal Bisma* 13(3):196–203.

- Nuha, Sukma Uli, Muhammad Miqdad, and Agung Budi Sulistiyo. 2021. "The Implementation Internal Control System Government With Government Regulation Release of No.60/2008 in KPU Jember Regency: A Phenomenology Approach." *Jurnal Riset Akuntansi Dan Bisnis Airlangga* 6(2):1091–1107.
- Nurkhasanah, N. 2019. "Pengaruh Kompetensi Aparatur, Partisipasi Masyarakat Dan Pemanfaatan Teknologi Informasi Terhadap Akuntabilitas Pengelolaan Dana Desa: Studi Kasus Desa Di Kecamatan Pancur Kab." *Rembang (Doctoral Dissertation, UIN Walisongo)*.
- Prasetyo, Whedy. 2019. "Akuntansi 4.0: Belajar Transdisipliner Momong, Among, Ngemong." *Journal of Research and Applications: Accounting and Management* 3(3). doi: 10.18382/jraam.v3i3.217.
- Prasetyo, Whedy, Rochman Effendi, Indah Purnamawati, and Resha Dwi Ayu Pangesti Mulyono. 2020. "'Cheryl' Information Technology As A Media To Enhance Competitive Advantages In E-Commerce." *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC & TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH* 9:2.
- Purnamawati, Indah, Bunga Maharani, Aisa Tri Agustini, Ririn Irmadariyani, Yosefa Sayekti, Djoko Supatmoko, and Bayu Aprillianto. 2019. "Implementation Of Strategic Corporate Social Responsibility Model Of Plantation Companies In Pandhalungan Area: A Comparative Study." *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC & TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH* 8(11):164–70.
- Purniawan, Yuda, Imam Mas'ud, and Novi Wulandari. 2019. "Penerapan Metode Variable Costing Dalam Perhitungan Harga Pokok Produksi Untuk Menentukan Harga Jual." *Jurnal Akuntansi Universitas Jember* 17(2).
- Putra, I. Made Yoga Darma, and Ni Ketut Rasmini. 2019. "Pengaruh Akuntabilitas, Transparansi, Dan Partisipasi Masyarakat Pada Efektivitas Pengelolaan Dana Desa." *E-Jurnal Akuntansi* 28(1):132–58.
- Putri, Harwidhea Dewantari, Muhammad Miqdad, and Agung Budi Sulistiyo. 2020a. "The Effect of Environmental Performance and CSR on Financial Performance of Manufacturing Companies in Indonesia." *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science* (2147- 4478) 9(6):50–57. doi: 10.20525/ijrbs.v9i6.913.
- Putri, Harwidhea Dewantari, Muhammad Miqdad, and Agung Budi Sulistiyo. 2020b. "The Effect of Environmental Performance and CSR on Financial Performance of Manufacturing Companies in Indonesia." *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science* (2147- 4478) 9(6):50–57. doi: 10.20525/ijrbs.v9i6.913.
- Roos Ana, Selvia, Agung Budi Sulistiyo, and Whedy Prasetyo. 2021. "The Effect of Intellectual Capital and Good Corporate Governance on Company Value Mediated by Competitive Advantage." *Journal of Accounting and Investment* 22(2). doi: 10.18196/ja.
- Roziq, Ahmad, Faqih Ulil Abshor, Agung Budi Sulistiyono, and Sumani Sumani. 2019. "Islamic Humanity: A New Approach to Minimizing Non-Performing Financing at the Islamic Bank in Indonesia." *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business* 7(12):1149–58. doi: 10.13106/JAFEB.2020.VOL7.NO12.1149.
- Roziq, Ahmad, Ayang Marizca, and Alwan Sri Kustono. 2021. "Testing the Efficiency of Capital Structure and Assets Structure in Bank." *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting* 105–12. doi: 10.9734/ajeba/2021/v21i230354.
- Roziq, Ahmad, Septarina Prita Dania Sofianti, Wasito, and Agung Budi Sulistiyo. 2019. "Pengaruh Modal Manusia Dan Struktur Aset Terhadap Risiko Kredit Dan Kinerja Keuangan Pada Bank Konvensional Di Indonesia." *Jurnal Bisma* 13(2):131–38.

- Roziq, Ahmad, and Hari Sukarno. 2021. "The Effect of Islamic Financing Schemes on Risk and Financing Performance in Islamic Banks in Indonesia." *IQTISHODUNA: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam* 10(1):17. doi: 10.36835/iqtishoduna.v10i1.729.
- Sains, Fakultas Sosial. 2018. "Analisis Pengaruh Pengelolaan Keuangan Daerah, Akuntabilitas Dan Transparansi Terhadap Kinerja Keuangan Pemerintah."
- Santosa Putra, Hendrawan, Abdul Rohman, Tri Jatmiko Wahyu Probowo, and Wahyu Agus Winarno. 2020. "ACCRUAL-BASED GOVERNMENT FINANCIAL REPORTING INFORMATION SYSTEM: ACCEPTANCE MODEL FROM AN INDONESIAN MUNICIPAL GOVERNMENT." *PJAE* 17(6).
- Satriawan, Raja Adri, and Debi Putri Pertiwi. 2015. "Pengaruh Akuntabilitas, Transparansi, Dan Pengawasan Terhadap Pengelolaan Anggaran Berkonsep Value For Money Pada Instansi Pemerintah (Studi Empiris Skpd Provinsi Riau)."
- Sinaga, Latifah. 2017. "Pengaruh Akuntabilitas, Transparansi Dan Pengawasan Terhadap Kinerja Anggaran Berkonsep Value for Money Pada Instansi Pemerintah Di Kabupaten Batu Bara."
- Sudewi, Ketut Novi, Nyoman Trisna Herawati, S. E. AK, Gede Adi Yuniarta, and S. E. AK. 2017. "Pengaruh Akuntabilitas, Transparansi, Komitmen Organisasi, Dan Pengawasan Terhadap Pengelolaan Anggaran Berkonsep Value For Money Pada Satuan Kerja Perangkat Daerah (SKPD) Kabupaten Buleleng." *JIMAT (Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa Akuntansi) Undiksha* 8(2).
- Sukmawati, Fitri, and Alfi Nurfitriani. 2019. "Pengaruh Transparansi Dan Akuntabilitas Terhadap Pengelolaan Keuangan Desa." *Jurnal Ilmiah Bisnis, Pasar Modal Dan Umkm* 2(1):52–66.
- Sulistiyo, Agung Budi, Riza Dewi al Ardi, and Ahmad Roziq. 2020. "IMPLEMENTASI THE NEW FRAUD TRIANGLE MODEL DENGAN PERSPEKTIF SYARIAH DALAM MENDETEKSI PERILAKU FRAUD." *EKUITAS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Keuangan)* 4(1):21–46. doi: 10.24034/j25485024.y2020.v4.i1.4324.
- Suyitno, Edy, Muhammad Miqdad, and Yosefa Sayekti. 2020. "The Effect of Local Own Revenue and General Allocation Funds on Capital Expenditures in East Java, Indonesia." *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*.
- Winarno, Wahyu Agus, Alwan Sri Kustono, Rochman Effendi, Imam Mas, and Oktaviani Ari Wardhaningrum. 2021. "Corporate Social Responsibility and Tax Avoidance: Evidence from Indonesia." *AKRUAL: Jurnal Akuntansi* 13(1):2085–9643. doi: 10.26740/jaj.v13n1.p.